

СЎЗ САЊАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

6 ЖИЛД, 3 СОН

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА

ТОМ 6, НОМЕР 3

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

VOLUME 6, ISSUE 3

СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА | INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

№3 (2023) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-9297-2023-3>

Бош муҳаррир:
Тўхтасинов Илҳом
п.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Бош муҳаррир ўринбосари:

Главный редактор:
Тухтасинов Илхом
д.п.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Заместитель главного редактора:

Editor in Chief:
Tuhtasinov Ilhom
DSc. Professor (Uzbekistan)

Deputy Chief Editor

ТАҲРИРИЙ МАСЛАҲАТ КЕНГАШИ

Назаров Бахтиёр
академик. (Ўзбекистон)

Якуб Умарўғли
ф.ф.д., профессор (Туркия)

Алмаз Улви Биннатова
ф.ф.д., профессор (Озарбайжон)

Бокиева Гуландом
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Миннуллин Ким
ф.ф.д., профессор (Татаристон)

Махмудов Низомиддин
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Керимов Исмаил
ф.ф.д., профессор (Россия)

Жўраев Маматкул
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Куренов Рахиммаед
к.ф.н. (Туркменистон)

Кристофер Жеймс Форт
Мичиган университети (АҚШ)

Умархўжаев Мухтор
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Мирзаев Ибодулло
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Болтабоев Ҳамидулла
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Дўстмухаммедов Хуршид
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Лиходзиевский А.С.
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Сиддикова Ирода
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Шиукашвили Тамар
ф.ф.д. (Грузия)

Юсупов Ойбек
масъул котиб, доцент (Ўзбекистон)

РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ СОВЕТ

Назаров Бахтиёр
академик. (Узбекистан)

Якуб Умар оглы
д.ф.н., профессор (Туркия)

Алмаз Улви Биннатова
д.ф.н., профессор (Азербайджан)

Бакиева Гуландом
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Миннуллин Ким
д.ф.н., профессор (Татарстан)

Махмудов Низомиддин
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Керимов Исмаил
д.ф.н., профессор (Россия)

Джураев Маматкул
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Куренов Рахыммаед
к.ф.н. (Туркменистан)

Кристофер Джеймс Форт
Университет Мичигана (США)

Умархаджаев Мухтар
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Мирзаев Ибодулло
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Балтабоев Ҳамидулла
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Дустмухаммедов Хуршид
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Лиходзиевский А.С.
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Сиддикова Ирода
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Шиукашвили Тамар
д.ф.н. (Грузия)

Юсупов Ойбек
отв. секретарь, доцент (Узбекистан)

EDITORIAL BOARD

Bakhtiyor Nazarov
academician. (Uzbekistan)

Yakub Umarogli
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Turkey)

Almaz Ulvi Binnatova
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Azerbaijan)

Bakieva Gulandom
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Minnulin Kim
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Tatarstan)

Mahmudov Nizomiddin
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Kerimov Ismail
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Russia)

Juraev Mamatkul
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Kurenov Rakhimmamed
Ph.D. Ass. Prof. (Turkmenistan)

Christopher James Fort
University of Michigan (USA)

Umarkhodjaev Mukhtar
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Mirzaev Ibodulla
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Boltaboev Hamidulla
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Dustmuhammedov Khurshid
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Lixodzievsky A.S.
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Siddiqova Iroda
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Shiukashvili Tamar
Doc. of philol. scien. (Georgia)

Yusupov Oybek
Ass. prof. (Uzbekistan) - Senior Secretary

PageMaker | Верстка | Саҳифаловчи: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

1. Qobilov Usmon Uralovich ALISHER NAVOIY SHE'RIYATI OBRAZLAR OLAMI VA BADIYYAT MASALASI.....	5
2. Abror MURTAZAYEV NORMATIV-HUQUQIY Hujjatlarni matnini lingvistik ekspertiza qilishning turlari.....	12
3. Abdug'aniyeva Iroda Abbos qizi SPEECH ACT THEORY AND ITS CLASSIFICATIONS.....	19
4. Sadriddinzoda Safiya Shaxobiddinovna O'ZBEK, RUS VA INGLIZ TILIDAGI FOLKLORNING DEMOOLGIK VA MIFOLOGIK PERSONAJLARNI TAQQOSLASH.....	24
5. Saliyeva Ziroat Zokirovna YOZISHNI ORQITISHNING XUSUSIYATLARI VA YONDASHUVLARI.....	29
6. Габбובה А.Қ., Алиева М.И., Мехтиева З. Х. ОСОБЕННОСТИ КОМПСТИРОВАНИЯ СЕЛЬСКОХОЗЯЙСТВЕННЫХ ОТХОДОВ С ЧАСТИЦАМИ РАЗНОГО РАЗМЕРА.....	35
7. Нодира Аззамовна Исакова ЎЗБЕК ТИЛИДАГИ ЎЗЛАШМАЛАРНИ ТАСНИФЛАШ ВОСИТАЛАРИ.....	40
8. Tagayeva Tamara Baxodirovna U.S.MAUGHAM BADIY USLUBINING INDIVIDUAL XUSUSIYATLARI.....	47
9. Усманова Салиха Юлдашевна, Хайдарова Гулбахор Юлдашевна ОСОБЕННОСТИ ИНТЕГРАТИВНО - ДИФФЕРЕНЦИРОВАННОЙ СИСТЕМЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ГРАМОТЕ СТУДЕНТОВ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ ГРУПП.....	53
10. Тагаева Сайёра Улашевна, Мустанова Шохиста Артиковна MUTTER/ ОНА КОНЦЕПТИНИНГБАДИИЙ МАТНЛАРДА ВОКЕЛАНИШИ.....	58
11. Hamroyeva Farida Faxriddinovna “BABYLON REVISITED” VA “IMON” NOVELLALARIDA MAVZUGA OID NARRATIVLI TRANSPOZISIYA XUSUSIDA.....	63
12. Shapsanova Feruza Muzaffarovna PESSIMISTIC MOOD TOWARD HUMAN NATURE DEPICTED IN THE NOVEL “THE UNICORN” BY IRIS MURDOCH.....	68
13. Buranova Lola Uktamovna FORMING THE SKILLS OF MONOLOGUE AND DIALOGUE SPEECH IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE.....	75
14. Umarova Oyzoda Solijonovna, Farhodova Shahzoda Umidovna INGLIZ TILI SHAKLLARINING SOTSIOLOGIY TADQIQI.....	81
15. Ziyadullayev Abubakir Ibodulla o'g'li ALFRED DE MYUSSE ASARLARIDAGI BADIY ZAMON TASNIFI.....	86
16. Abdusalamova Lobar Akbar Qizi CH. AYTMATOV IJODI VA XX ASR SO'NGGI CHORAGIDAGI INGLIZ ADABIYOTSHUNOSLIGI (“Alvido, Gulsari!” qissasi misolida).....	90
17. Tursunova Parvina, Tuychiyeva Maxchexra, Abdullayeva Parvina O'QUV-PEDAGOGIK JARAYONINI INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA TASHKIL ETISH.....	97
18. Kadirova Dilfuza Alisherovna O'ZBEK TILIDA MAQTOV KONSEPTINING VERBALIZATSIYASI.....	102

19. Botirova Maxliyo O‘ZBEK TILSHUNOSLIGIDA REKLAMA MATNLARI TADQIQIGA DOIR ISHLAR TAHLILI.....	106
20. Zakirova Madina Damirovna MAIN LINGUISTIC APPROACHES TO THE INVESTIGATION OF FOREGROUNDING.....	112
21. Бобоев Улаш Нейматович ЭФФЕКТИВНЫЕ СТРАТЕГИИ ПЕРЕВОДА СРЕДСТВ ШОК-ТЕЙМЕНТА В УЗБЕКСКИХ И ФРАНЦУЗСКИХ ПУБЛИЦИСТИЧЕСКИХ ТЕКСТАХ НА РУССКИЙ ЯЗЫК.....	120
22. Atabayeva Zarnigor Baxran qizi JAHON ADABIYOTIDA DEMONIZATSIIYA MOTIVI, UNING GENEZISI VA ANAMIYATI.....	126
23. Джураев Ботир Илхомович ИНГЛИЗ ТИЛИДА МИҚДОРИЙ АСПЕКТУАЛЛИКНИНГ СИНТАКТИК ИФОДАЛАНИШИ.....	133
24. Балясникова Марина Александровна К ЭТИМОГРАФИИ СИМВОЛА “РАДУГА” В ИНДОЕВРОПЕЙСКИХ ЯЗЫКАХ.....	138
25. Ташбекова Дилором Исмаиловна, Вохидова Нигора Абдузугуровна ПОНЯТИЕ «ЯЗЫК» В РУССКОМ ЯЗЫКОЗНАНИИ (ВТОРАЯ ПОЛОВИНА XIX - НАЧАЛО XX ВЕКА).....	145
26. Roza Timonova, Khadicha Suyarova THE IMPACT OF LINGUISTIC PECULIARITIES IN ADVERTISING LANGUAGE: A STUDY ON PUNS, METAPHORS, AND SLOGANS.....	150
27. Ёринова О. ЧОРВАЧИЛИК ТЕРМИНЛАРИ ЁРТАСИДА ГИПОНИМИЯ ХОДИСАНИНГ ШАКЛЛАНИШИ.....	155
28. Камалходжаева Саида Саидахмадовна ПРАНК КАК ОБЪЕКТ СУДЕБНОЙ ЛИНГВИСТИКИ.....	160
29. Koziyeva Iqbol Komiljonovna KELIB SHIQISH TURKIY BO‘LGAN RUS FAMILIYALARI.....	163
30. Юнусова Диёра Аминовна СИНТАКСЫ, ВЫРАЖЕННЫЕ ОТНОСИТЕЛЬНЫМ МЕСТОИМЕНИЕМ THAT В ПОЗИЦИИ ЯДЕРНОГО ПРЕДИЦИРУЕМОГО КОМПОНЕНТА.....	170
31. Xudoyberdiyeva Gulmira Allaberdi Qizi AYRIM OMONIM TERMINLARNING LEKSIKOGRAFIK VA LINGVOSTATISTIK TAHLILI.....	175
32. Xolova Muyassar Abdulhakimovna SURXONDARYO VILOYATI SHEVALARINING O‘ZBEK MILLIY DIALECTAL KORPUSIDA REPREZINTATIVLIGI.....	180
33. Nilufar Abduraxmonova, Saodat Boysariyeva TABIIY TILNI QAYTA ISHLASHDA (NLP) OKKAZIONALIZMLARNING MORFEM TAHLILI.....	188

ISSN: 2181-9297

www.tadqiqot.uz

Shapsanova Feruza MuzaffarovnaTeacher at Uzbekistan state world languages university,
“Linguistic and English literature” department**PESSIMISTIC MOOD TOWARD HUMAN NATURE DEPICTED IN THE NOVEL “THE UNICORN” BY IRIS MURDOCH** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8249752>**ANNOTATION**

The article deals with the philosophically coated novel “The Unicorn”, written by prominent English writer, Iris Murdoch. Iris Murdoch was born in 1919, in Dublin, Ireland, however, she moved to London in her early ages, got education and gave lectures at Oxford University on philosophy. The aim of the research is to analyze the novel “The Unicorn” to reveal its philosophical and aesthetic values. “The Unicorn” is the author’s seventh novel which published in 1963. Depicting the dark atmosphere and mood in its leading characters and setting, most critics believe it to be the gothic novel. To reach our aim we used several methods including empirical, historical – cultural, analytical methods. We tried to investigate philosophical aspects raised in the novel about human nature. As a research results, we detected the moral and aesthetic value of the novel. Murdoch implied her own philosophical view about ego-centric nature of people into the novel with artistic interpretation.

Key words: gothic novel, philosophy, morality, art, truth, ego, existentialism, alienation

Шапсанова Феруза МузаффаровнаПреподаватель в Узбекском государственном
университете мировых языков, кафедра
“Лингвистика и английская литература”**ПЕССИМИСТИЧЕСКОЕ ОТНОШЕНИЕ К ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОЙ ПРИРОДЕ,
ИЗОБРАЖЕННОЕ В РОМАНЕ АЙРИС МЕРДОК “ЕДИНОРОГ”****АННОТАЦИЯ**

Статья посвящена философски окрашенному роману “Единорог”, написанному выдающейся английской писательницей Айрис Мердок. Айрис Мердок родилась в 1919 году в Дублине, Ирландия, однако в раннем возрасте она переехала в Лондон, получила образование и читала лекции по философии в Оксфордском университете. Целью исследования является анализ романа “Единорог” с целью выявления его философских и эстетических ценностей. “Единорог” - седьмой роман автора, опубликованный в 1963 году. Изображая мрачную атмосферу и настроение главных героев и обстановки, большинство критиков считают его готическим романом. Для достижения нашей цели мы использовали несколько методов, включая эмпирические, историко-культурные, аналитические. Мы попытались исследовать философские аспекты, затронутые в романе о человеческой природе. В результате исследования мы выявили моральную и эстетическую ценность романа. Мердок

внесла в роман свой собственный философский взгляд на эгоцентричную природу людей с помощью художественной интерпретации.

Ключевые слова: готический роман, философия, мораль, искусство, истина, эго, экзистенциализм, отчуждение

Shapsanova Feruza Muzaffarovna

O'zbekiston davlat jahon tillari universiteti

“Lingvistika va ingliz adabiyoti” kafedrası o'qituvchisi

AYRIS MYORDOKNING "YAKKASHOX" ROMANIDA TASVIRLANGAN INSON TABIATIGA NISBATAN PESSIMISTIK KAYFIYAT

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada taniqli ingliz yozuvchisi Ayris Myordok tomonidan yozilgan falsafiy roman "Yakkashox" haqida so'z boradi. Ayris Myordok 1919 - yilda Dublin, Irlandiyada tug'ilgan. Bunga qaramasdan, u erta yoshida Londonga ko'chib o'tdi, ta'lim oldi va Oksford universitetida falsafa sohasi bo'yicha ma'ruzalar berdi. Tadqiqotning maqsadi "Yakkashox" romanini tahlil qilib, uning falsafiy va estetik qiymatini yoritib berishdir. "Yakkashox" muallifning ettinchi romani bo'lib, 1963 yilda nashr etilgan. Makonda tasvirlangan qorong'u atmosfera, yolg'iz va daxshatga tushgan qahramonlar sababli tanqidchilar asarni gotik roman deb hisoblashadi. Maqsadimizga erishish uchun biz empirik, tarixiy – madaniy, analitik metodlardan foydalandik. Biz romanda inson tabiati haqidagi falsafiy jihatlarini o'rganishga harakat qildik. Tadqiqot natijalari sifatida biz romanning axloqiy va estetik qiymatini aniqladik. Myordok badiiy talqin yordamida odamlarning egoistik tabiati haqidagi o'zining falsafiy qarashlarini romanda aks ettirgan.

Kalit so'zlar: gotik roman, falsafa, axloq, san'at, haqiqat, ego, ekzistensializm, begonalashish

Introduction

Iris Murdoch started her writing career with the novel “Under the Net” (1954) which contains some philosophical ideas. After this novel she became famous as a founder of philosophical tendencies in contemporary English literature. Murdoch is a prolific writer who created more than thirty novels implying philosophical and aesthetical views on them. In the middle of her literary career, Murdoch turned her attention to the dark side of human nature, putting philosophical question - how to overcome our egocentric nature which leads to evil actions. In the novel “The Unicorn”, the author tries to find answer for this philosophical question with artistic description, keeping its aesthetic value. Iris Murdoch's “The Unicorn” is claimed to be a philosophical and gothic novel. “The Unicorn” is called gothic because its imaginative impulse was drawn from medieval buildings and ruins, hence commonly used settings in the novel are castles. Besides, dark atmosphere with antagonistic heroes dominates in the novel. Iris Murdoch implied some existential themes in her novel such as: isolation, alienation and unbearable heaviness of freedom. Some critics suggest that, while choosing the title of the novel Iris Murdoch got inspiration from the five pieces of Red Series of unicorn tapestries in the Musee National du Moyen Age. When she visited France, Paris, she saw the picture which influenced her psychologically to put a unicorn as a title of her book.

Main Part

The plot of the novel is dramatic, yet it's written in a very traditional way with conflicts, climax, and resolution. “The Unicorn” consists of chapters within seven parts. Each part includes approximately 35, 36 chapters. The story held by the outsiders in the novel which is significant feature of Murdoch's novels that taken from French existentialists. The shreds of evidence in “The Unicorn” follows a tutor named Marian Taylor. She decides to get a job in the Gaze Castle, West Ireland which she finds in the advertisement and responds because of the failure in love relationship with her ex-lover Geoff. Besides, she is drawn to the announced high salary and also the chance to teach French and Italian. However, the most important thing is that Marian suffers from a shortage of adventure and desires to fulfill her life. Thus, Marian arrives in Ireland and meets by tall and attractive Gerald

Scottow, who takes her to the Gaze Castle. On the road they pass by the neighbor castle - Rider, where professor Max Lejour and his adult children Pip and Alice live. Max Lejour is often visited by his pupil Effingham Cooper. When Marian arrives at the Gaze castle, she finds that her pupil isn't a child, but the lady of the castle - a woman named Mrs. Crean-Smith. Quietly, it is discovered that Hannah is imprisoned in the castle by her husband Peter Crean-Smith against her wishes. Effingham Cooper's visits to his former teacher's house initially have another intention. He has fallen in love with Hannah, at the same time, Max's daughter Alice has feelings for Effingham. Even though, she has already adjusted herself that Effingham would never love her. Max Lejour is an image of a philosopher. He often discusses the philosophical issues about human nature with Effingham. They characterize the unicorn's image of a Christ-like scapegoat: he is innocent and used to atone for others' sins. Hannah appears to be the symbol of a unicorn. When Hannah's husband learns that she has an affair with Pip, he imprisons her for adultery. She has been imprisoned for seven years. It seems that time has come to change everything, because seven years have its own legend, as in fairytales. Gerald Scottow is another character, has a role of a jailor for Hannah engaged by Peter Crean-Smith. Marian Taylor and other inhabitants of Gaze castle have intricate love relationships. Due to her unhappy love life, she is eager to leave London. Her pupil, Hannah Crean-Smith is confined by her husband, Peter, whose twisted view of love makes him imagine that he is acting to protect her as much as punish her. Marian enchanted by Hannah wants to rescue her and asks for Effingham's help, so they together plan her escape. Unfortunately, their plan fails, because Alice stops them by force. When Hannah finally makes her mind and decides to escape, she shoots Gerald Scottow, and commits suicide throwing herself out of the cliff. Hannah's husband Peter is killed by Hannah's loyal servant, Nolan. In the end, Hannah's lover Pip who is isolated from the outer world hangs himself.

In her article, published in London Magazine in 1968, Murdoch wrote: "The notion of the intrusion of demons – well, I feel this is something that happens in life. Not necessarily that people really are demons but that they play the role of demons for other people." [Rose, 1968; 69]. The existential theory which has been greatly changed is widely regarded in literature as the inspiration for Murdoch's books written in the 1950s and 1960s. Thus, according to numerous experts, the author's existential enthusiasm evolved over time and was eventually supplanted by the creation of her own ethical and aesthetic system based on Platonism. The novelist, who is inclined to questioning life's purpose, has a strong urge to highlight the philosophical topic in its purest form, simplifying the scenario to a set of ideas and the characters to mere messengers of those views. Any haphazard, nonexistent aspects of modern life were to be left in the narrative for the least amount of time possible. As a result, the work "The Unicorn" arose as a complicated, difficult-to-understand piece.

Iris Murdoch investigated several themes in her novel. Isolation from the outer world is one of the significant motifs in her work. In the novel, religious allusion was taken as a symbol that contains in unicorn or the notion which was popular in the Middle Ages - unicorn in captivity. Unicorn from Christian religion's point of view is the symbol of Christ, who refers to purity, innocence and sacrifice. In the novel, the leading character Hannah explicitly is shown as a symbol of Unicorn, as a victim of all evilness. However, the author puts additional equivocal meaning to the notion unicorn and the characters who believed to be the one. During the novel evidences, Murdoch researches the human nature, its ego, and how some individuals tend to produce evilness under the role of victim. Hannah is a great example to prove this philosophical attitude. She is a victim, but also a guilty one. All people compassionately look at her, try to help, to release from her jail. Hanna unintentionally adjusts to the condition, making others suffer for her. At the end of the novel, we see existential wakening in her state. She realizes her own ego-centric nature and decides to end up her role of victim by committing suicide. Another important theme is opposition of reality and fantasy. Apart from Hannah, other characters have their own intentions by playing the role of saviors, or knights like in a fairy tale. Their main intention is to withdrawal from bitter and meaningless reality into romantic fairytale.

The novel consists of opposite characters. The main character of the novel is believed to be Hannah Crean-Smiths by major people. Hannah is the unicorn of the title, a rare and mysterious creature who enchants all around her, but is inaccessible to everyone. Both whore and goddess,

murderess and saint, she is either a wretched prisoner or a willing recluse. Unknowable and unreachable, she enchants all around her. The love that each character feels for her is encompassed the full range of human affection. Since, her reality is impossible to know, she becomes the reflection of each character's fantasy about her. Like the unicorn, she is a test of the purity and innocence of the others in her own guilt and suffering. Her opposite counterpart is Marian Taylor, Londoner, who comes to Gaze to tutor Hannah and decides to help her escape. When the plan goes south, she must face her complicity in the tragic deaths. Gerald Scottow is Gaze Castle's keeper, who functions as Hannah's jailer. He is formerly Peter's lover, but currently is involved with Jamesie Evercreech, the estate's chauffeur, who once helps Hannah to run away. The middle-aged Scottow relies on his good looks and reputation for supernatural gifts, as well as his physical strength which helps him maintain control. Another important character is Denis Nolan, the clerk of Gaze, who becomes Marian's accomplice in aiding Hannah to escape. Devoted to his mistress, he enjoys singing to her, but his fear of Gerald is paralyzing. He leaves Gaze after she dies. His counterpart is Jamesie. The characters are not negative nor positive. Rather they include both features, good and evil. The outsiders in the novel, Marian and Effie strongly embodied with the idea of rescuing Hannah. Although struggling a lot they can't change anything as they never participate in this isolated and strange evidence. The characters in "The Unicorn" additionally take upon themselves the author's task: they create fictional roles for themselves and for other characters. Even the novel's sensationalistic ending is brought about by their subconscious awareness of generic conventions.

Iris Murdoch points out that, in a progressively secular culture the breakdown of faith manifests itself in the absence of a shared moral basis, driving people apart, for "old God symbolized, namely, the idea of the Good as the source of an absolute moral claim on human life". [Antonaccio, 2007; 15-22]. Mankind has indeed been abandoned in a spiritual gap as a result of the loss of faith as a moral guide; Murdoch argued that philosophy could replace religion to get people reach the 'truth'. As she was well-versed in philosophical studies, she was able to establish a moral philosophy through which individuals may lead themselves in their search for 'goodness.'

Murdoch's major concentration was on characterization, as she exposed her beliefs through philosophical and literary works, mirroring her Platonist roots. People do not have complete access to the truth throughout their lives since perception does not fully reflect reality. People only have "intimations of truth" as a result. This concept of awareness of reality - portrayed through Murdoch's characters - is equal to their spiritual progress, with the righteous having a larger vision of Truth, as shown in her books. [Browning, 1993].

Considering literature as a sort of moral instruction, Iris Murdoch presents her views on life and ethical behavior more clearly through her novels. Murdoch strives to educate humanity which road to go toward moral perfection by carefully building complicated characters that push towards 'Good' or 'Evil.' Individuals may better comprehend how the veil of illusion distorts one's vision of Reality and Truth by creating this sort of binary opposition. This feature of Iris Murdoch's characterization is clearly expressed in "The Unicorn". Her choice to engage in the Gothic mode allows her to explore the origins and representations of 'Evil' by analysing the "human psyche and its obsessive desires, murderous impulses and dysfunctional fantasies". Writing in this mode also gives her the chance to "explore the possibility that evil is not just the absence of good, but a dynamic force to be recognized and rejected by those pursuing moral goodness". [Rowe, 2010; 70-71]. To put it another way, the potential that one's soul is polluted by the forces of Evil must be acknowledged in order to pursuit the moral Goodness to overcome this egocentric tendency.

Murdoch believes suffering to be always morally imperfect, because distress stems from the unawareness of truth. As part of the human condition, pain becomes dangerous in the sense that the one grieving draws those around him into his own suffering, which in turn becomes a source of power. In the novel, this process is explained by the use of the Greek concept - Ate:

"Ate is the name of the almost automatic transfer of suffering from one being to another. Power is a form of Ate. The victims of power, and any power has its victims, are themselves infected. They have then to pass it on, to use power on others. This is evil, and the crude image of the all-powerful God is a sacrilege. Good is not exactly powerless. For to be powerless, to be a complete victim, may

be another source of power. But Good is non- powerful. And it is in the good that Ate is finally quenched, when it encounters a pure being who only suffers and does not attempt to pass the suffering on.” [Murdoch, 1963; 92-93].

This transference of suffering can be seen through the habitants of Gaze castle. Hannah's agony is felt by everyone around her, and she gains strength from this empathy and fixation with her suffering throughout the story. Her dearest friends as well as oppressors idolize her, transforming her into an ethereal figure, too pure to be touched, too fragile and hesitant, virtuous, Holy and Divine... The other characters at Gaze are imprisoned by feeling passionate love toward Hannah; their souls have become captives of her cunning control. Nevertheless, at the end of the novel, Hannah herself breaks the idea of being pure and virtuous, admitting that her suffering is manipulative and selfish.: "Ah, how much I need you all! I have battered upon you like a secret vampire... I lived by your belief in my suffering. But I had no real suffering". [Murdoch, 1963; 213].

Hannah murders her jailor, Gerald, who has substituted her husband, to begin the countdown of genuine misery from that point on. The reader can easily confuse Hannah's psychic personality. By analyzing the novel, we've come to question: Is Hannah a corrupted creature engrossed in the dark, insane desire of destruction, or a lonely lady with a noble spirit who abandoned the world? We see that in this novel everything is ambiguous and confusing, each thought is contradictory, and the path of the events is uncertain. The fundamental theme is the depressing notion of freedom's impossibility, as well as the weirdly designed existence. "In the field of morality, we are all prisoners," suggests Max Lezhur, the philosopher who studies Plato, "but freedom cannot cure us..." All efforts to rescue Hannah, to bring her back to reality, to a regular existence have failed. When the game is ended, and Hannah's secret is discovered there is only one thing left to do, end up dying. She is adamant about not entering the real world.

During Mr Crean-Smith's absence Gerald begins to substitute the master's and villain's roles: "he has become like him. He has become him... Gerald is Peter now. He has Peter's place, he is possessed by Peter, he even looks like Peter". [Murdoch, 1963; 229]. As a result, Murdoch develops an engrossing scenario complete with a classic duplicate character who becomes a mirror of the master's inner aspirations. Hannah appears to be a Gothic heroine at first glance, whereas Mr Crean-Smith has a role of a tyrant. Marian, after some time discovers that Hannah is an enchantress who makes everybody believe in her purity as well as her self-imposed confinement, lives under the same misconception. [Deborah, 1987; 102]. Mr Crean-Smith, who embodies a villain pretends to be a sufferer who had escaped death at Hannah's hands, but falls victim to her servant. Her boyfriend - Philip faces a similar fate when he supposedly shoots himself by mistake. "Hannah had claimed her last victim". [Murdoch, 1963; 269]. This and other cases from the book support Hannah's argument that she is the oppressor not just to others, but most significantly to herself. The unusual heroine, who merely looks to be quiet has the bravery to create her own imprisonment, force her husband down the cliff, or commit suicide. Thus, it comes as no surprise that no matter how much Marian tries to convince Hannah that: "she won't die if she goes outside the walls" [Murdoch, 1963; 120], she is not able to force the mistress to do it. The very attempt to cross the symbolic border between the inside and the outside is doomed to failure. After the attempted escape, Gerald explains to Marian: "What can you do for her, do you think, for her with the years and years of this solitude within her, by simply, as you say, 'showing her the outside'? Do you think this would mean anything? Do you think there really is, for Hannah, an inside and an outside anymore?". [Murdoch, 1963; 150]. Hannah has become oblivious to the existence of the outside world as a result of her years of self-entrapment, and she sees no need to break the cycle. Any attempt to save Hannah is bound to fail since she has lost her awareness of outside world, and the concept of freedom has a different meaning for her than it does for Marian. Marian is unaware of Hannah's mental captivity and interprets her mistress's behavior as a lack of courage in the face of Mr Crean-Smith's persecution. Hannah is said to have realized that she can no longer exist in her cell but also, she does not belong in the outer world. Her fate can be likened to Plato's Cave parabola, especially the way in which Deborah Johnson presents this motif following the words of Luce Irigaray: "the Platonic image of the Cave proposes a set of oppositions, differences, discontinuities between outside and inside". [Deborah, 1987; 88]. However, the critic

draws attention to the fact that Murdoch more often than not “deflects and alters the significance of those philosophical statements and metaphors which she inscribes into her narrative. It is not surprising therefore that the Cave, itself an image of illusion, should have in her narratives its dark and mysterious double as a site of potential truth.” [Deborah, 1987; 86-87]. This is why Hannah believes her life to be: “a dream. Do you know what part I have been playing? That of God, and do you know what I have been really? Nothing, a legend. A hand stretched out from the real world went through me as through a paper”. [Murdoch, 1963; 218]. According to Johnson, this and other examples demonstrate that Hannah's existence is imaginary, that she resided in the cave, and that the hand that created the illusion belonged to the characters, who “textualize” her. [Deborah, 1987; 68]. Hannah will die if she finally succumbed to the temptation of experiencing reality. This view may be questionable, given that the mistress, even if in a fictional universe, still performs the role of God, manipulating the lives of others as well as her own, as the master of puppets does. So, rather than the difficulties of facing reality, Hannah's decision to end her life reflects her dread of accepting the truth of her husband's returning and wrecking her false self. However, a close examination of Murdoch's philosophical works reveals certain Platonic similarities. To follow Conradi's line of argument, each of the characters of the novel represent a different theoretical approach towards the concept of freedom. Max Lejour is a typical Platonist, Marian is a feminist, whereas Effingham Cooper stands for existentialism. [Conradi, 1999; 19-30]. The entire book is set up in such a way that it subverts the simplistic notion of freedom. This is in line with a remark that Murdoch's resistance to the Romantic tradition, which gave rise to a neurotic contemporary story full of people that behave according to their whims and impulses rather than seeking the moral truth, is reflected through the figure of Hannah. [Murdoch, 1999; 217].

“... The selfish consciousness of the most people is blind to the perception of the true nature of the world, the rights and demands of other people, even the very existence of the Other,” in the letter to V.V. Ivasheva Murdoch explained her concept of illusion.

Murdoch's irony is a fusion of the sublime, magnificent, tragic, horrific, and silly, which manifests itself in many different ways and is presented in all aspects of human experience and existence. Such irony prevents comedy or tragedy from existing in its “pure” form, but it transforms the writer's vision of reality into a tragicomedy. By constructing an angelic monster, Murdoch demands from the reader to recognize the intrinsic brokenness of the human kind.

With “The Unicorn” Murdoch tries to convince the reader that “freedom is not choosing what is merely the move that we make when all is already lost. Freedom is knowing and understanding and respecting things quite other than ourselves”. [Murdoch, 1999; 284]. Marian is unable to realize this, as a result, her activities are ineffective and hurtful to the other individuals in the novel.

Murdoch's characters are able to be free along with love. “Love is the perception of individuals. Love is the extremely difficult realization that something other than oneself is real. Love, and so art and morals, is the discovery of reality” [Murdoch, 1999; 215] she writes in one of her theoretical works, while discussing the notion of freedom.

In conclusion, we want to say that the novel “Unicorn” is a great example of philosophically coated novel with gothic elements. In this work Iris Murdoch refers that life is full of sufferings and escapism from harsh reality into fantasies, self-created illusions is not a good option. Rejection of truth may lead to bad consequences, and the only way to overcome existential crisis, hollowness, loneliness, absurd life is to defeat self-relentless ego and accept or realize others existence and unique nature. Murdoch's moral philosophy emerges gradually throughout the book as a call for societal awareness. We can only focus on anything beyond the ‘Self’ if we recognize selfishness as a manifestation of ‘Evil’. By focusing on people and art while ignoring one's own self, one begins a road of enlightenment that will lead him to transform his perspective of Reality, eventually leading to the discovery of Truth - the secular rehabilitation of one's soul.

Iris Murdoch is claimed to be a famous writer who inclined philosophically in her best novels. Her intention through her novel is clear; they contain both aesthetical and philosophical values that teach us a moral lesson, at the same time entertains.

References

1. Antonaccio, M. (2007). Reconsidering Iris Murdoch's Moral Philosophy and Theology. In: Rowe, A. (eds) *Iris Murdoch: A Reassessment*. Palgrave Macmillan, London. P.p 15-22 <https://doi.org/10.1057/9780230625174>
2. Cheryl Browning. (1993). *Understanding Iris Murdoch*. Columbia: University of South Carolina Press.
3. Conradi, Peter J. (1999). Editor's preface. In *Iris Murdoch, Existentialists and mystics. Writings on philosophy and literature, 19-30*. London: Penguin Books.
4. Iris Murdoch (1963) *The Unicorn*. Chatto & Windus.
5. Johnson, Deborah. (1987). *Iris Murdoch*. Brighton: Harvester, Print. P 68-102.
6. Murdoch, Iris. (1999). *Existentialists and mystics. Writings on philosophy and literature*. Peter Conradi (ed.). London: Penguin Books.p.215-217
7. *Plato's Allegory of the Cave, Animated: History's Greatest Parable exploring the Nature of Reality*. Ted.Ed. <https://billeavitttherapy.com>
8. Rose, W. K. (1 June 1968). *Iris Murdoch, informally*. London Magazine. P.p 69
9. Rowe, Anne and Avril Horner, eds. (2010). *Iris Murdoch and Morality*. London: Palgrave Macmillan. p 70

4. D. Sulevmanov, A. Gatiatullin, N. Prokopyev and N. Abdurakhmonova, "Turkic Morpheme Web Portal as a Platform for Turkology Research," 2020 International Conference on Information Science and Communications Technologies (ICISCT), Tashkent, Uzbekistan, 2020, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/ICISCT50599.2020.9351500.
5. <https://uzbekcorpus.uz/>
6. Koskenniemi, K. (1983). Two-Level Model for Morphological Analysis. International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence.
7. Hozirgi o'zbek tili faol so'zlarining izohli lug'ati/ A. Hojiyev, A. Nurmonov, S. Zaynobiddinov va boshq. – T.: 2001
8. А.В. Чемышев Динамический лексикон: компьютерное представление моделей словообразования // *Turklang*, 2017 (II). – P.224.
9. Yuldashev J. Usmon Nosir she'riyati lingvopoetikasi : Filol. fan. falsafa doktori (PhD) diss. avtoreferati 2023.
10. Abduraxmonova, N. Z. "Linguistic support of the program for translating English texts into Uzbek (on the example of simple sentences): Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) il dis. aforef." (2018).
11. Alessandro Agostini, Timur Usmanov, Ulugbek Khamdamov, Nilufar Abdurakhmonova, and Mukhammadsaid Mamasaidov. 2021. UZWORDNET: A Lexical-Semantic Database for the Uzbek Language. In Proceedings of the 11th Global Wordnet Conference, pages 8–19, University of South Africa (UNISA). Global Wordnet Association.
12. Abdurakhmonova N, Tuliyeu U. Morphological analysis by finite state transducer for Uzbek-English machine translation/*Foreign Philology: Language. Literature, Education*. 2018(3):68.
13. Abdurakhmonova N, Urdishev K. Corpus based teaching Uzbek as a foreign language. *Journal of Foreign Language Teaching and Applied Linguistics (J-FLTAL)*. 2019;6(1-2019):131-7.
14. Abdurakhmonov N. Modeling Analytic Forms of Verb in Uzbek as Stage of Morphological Analysis in Machine Translation. *Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Research*. 2017;5(03):89-100.